

Analyses of Sensor Films on a Carbon Fibre

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ABSTRACT

The use of embedded sensors and actuators for condition assessment of machines and structures is on rising demand [1]. Composite parts with high demands on safety and a long economic life-time, e. g. parts in airplanes and blades of wind turbines, will be equipped with strain and impact sensitive sensors in future to monitor their load history. This will lead to a better understanding and a safer application of composite materials. Different types of sensors based on different physical effects are available.

Carbon fibre surfaces coated with magnetoelastic materials and structured by methods of micro-manufacturing can serve as strain- and tension-sensitive microsensor systems capable of supporting safety and health monitoring functions in parts made of composite materials. The fabrication method based on thin-film deposition technology and microstructuring by means of Focused Ion Beam (FIB) machining was developed. Carbon fibres with multiple layers deposited by physical or chemical vapour deposition techniques show novel properties. The characterisation of this spectrum of mechanical, electrical and physical properties is the topic of this research. The actual results of all examinations will be presented.

Keywords: Structural Health Monitoring, Magnetostriction, Villari Effect, Carbon Fibres, Thin-Film Deposition Technology

1 PRINCIPLE OF A MAGNETOELASTIC MICROSENSOR ON A CARBON FIBRE

For the design and optimisation of advanced composite materials, the mechanical strain of carbon fibres has to be known [2]. A measurement approach is to fabricate a magnetoelastic micro strain sensor taking advantage of the Villari effect directly on the carbon fibre. Exposing a magnetoelastic sample to strain changes the properties of the material; in particular the magnetic relative permeability μ_r . It is inverse to Joule's magnetostriction which is the change in shape (elongation or contraction) of a magnetic sample in a magnetising field [3]. This microsensor is created by a three-layer system consisting of NiFe45/55 as magnetoelastic material, Si₃N₄ as an insulation, and Cu as coil material. A FIB system is used for patterning the Cu layer to create a microcoil

(Fig. 1) [4]. Changes of the magnetic permeability μ_r of the magnetoelastic material under load can be detected by two different principles. Using a transformer configuration, the NiFe45/55 and Si_3N_4 layers are surrounded by two Cu coils (primary and secondary coil) positioned inline. Energising the primary coil, a voltage is induced in the secondary coil. If the magnetic permeability μ_r of the NiFe45/55 is changed due to strain in the microsensors, the electromagnetic coupling changes as well. As a result, the induced voltage changes in the secondary coil. Using the second configuration, only one coil is required. This coil is connected in parallel with a capacitor to create an oscillating *LC*-circuit. Changes in the magnetic permeability μ_r due to strain causes a change in inductivity of the inductor result in a shift of the resonance frequency of the oscillating circuit. Either strain-sensitive microsensors can be integrated into composite parts with a minimal effect on the composite structure.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the carbon fibre microsensor

To prove the feasibility of the concept, a 100:1 model of the instrumented fibre was fabricated. In this prototype, a voltage of 100 mV was induced by applying a mechanical stress of 3.5 MPa, indicating the feasibility of the concept [2].

2 MANUFACTURING OF MAGNETOELASTIC MICROSENSOR

2.1 Preparation of carbon fibres

Carbon fibres are manufactured as bundles and commercially available at a bundle size of at least 400 single fibres. Since the magnetoelastic microstrain sensor is manufactured by use of only one single fibre, a process for the separation of fibre bundles is necessary. Different methods are described to separate fibre bundles. It is possible to realise an individual separation of fibres by contact with a weak alkaline solution while the fibres are connected as one of the electrodes used for creating an electric field [5]. Another patent describes the separation of a fibre bundle leading it through water whilst being subjected to an additional, opposed flow. The bundle is passed continuously through the channel and the separated fibre filaments are withdrawn and taken up under equal tension [6].

Different methods for fibre separation have been tested: drawing of a single fibre, led through a small cannula, a separation technique applying a comb to carry out a mechanical separation, air and fluid flow methods, separation by gravity and the effect of ultrasound. Mechanical separation by means of combs or barrel rolls had the least effect or even destroyed the bundles after a short distance. Ultrasound slightly stimulates single-fibre movement within a fluid, but does not serve as a separation technique alone. The usage of a fluid flow showed the best results in all tests. Further development is needed to raise the usability of this separation technique.

Carbon fibres are commonly sized. Before the NiFe45/55 layer is deposited, the polymer size must be removed completely [7]. A thermal treatment or a chemical solution by acetone is currently used for desizing. Results of former investigations have described the use of methyl ethyl ketone for desizing. The chemical state of carbon at the fibre surface depends on this process. As a result of the desizing process, oxidised forms of carbon or an amorphous pyrolytic phase are possible [7]. This idea and its effects on the deposition quality of NiFe45/55 layers will be verified in the further continuation of this project. After the thermal treatment or dissolution of surface resin in an acetone dip for desizing, and following the separation, a single carbon fibre can be used for the deposition process.

2.2 Film deposition on carbon fibres

For depositing the strain gauge's layers, thin-film technologies were applied. However, classic planar technologies can not be used, since the fibre which serves as the substrate is round. The single carbon fibres are coated with three layers using different thin-film deposition processes. The deposition of NiFe45/55 and Cu are carried out by means of Physical Vapour Deposition (PVD). To obtain homogeneous layers with a constant thickness at the whole circumference, the carbon fibres are manually mounted in a special holder and rotated twice by 120° to be coated from three sides. Since deposition tests showed a low adhesion of NiFe45/55 on the carbon fibre surface, a 50 nm thick Cr layer is used to increase the bonding strength.

The deposition of the non-conductive Si₃N₄ as electrical insulation between NiFe45/55 and Cu is carried out in a Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapour Deposition (PECVD) process. Such a process coats all sides of the carbon fibre evenly; therefore no fibre rotation is required. The process pressure and temperature as well as the gas flow are kept constant. The layer thicknesses vary between 1 µm and 5 µm depending on the deposition times.

2.3 Fabricating of the coil system

After the deposition of the outer Cu layer, a spiral lead has to be created. This may be accomplished by means of a FIB system [8]. To allow cutting a spiral required for the coil, a fibre turning lathe was developed [9]. The fibre turning lathe is an add-on for the FIB system, which allowed the rotation of coated carbon fibre inside of the FIB's vacuum chamber. For cutting the spiral groove into the Cu coat, a focused Ga⁺ ion beam is used (Fig. 2). The last step of the microsensors fabrication includes the contacting of the coil. For the first (transformer) approach, both ends of the coils as well as the centre tab are connected, for the second case (inductor), only the two outer connections are required.

Figure 2: FIB processing of the microcoil

3 CHARACTERISATION METHODS AND RESULTS

To guarantee a reproducible and complete function of the magnetoelastic microsensor, perfect quality of coatings and machining is necessary. Reaching this condition is the priority of the present research activity. For the optimisation of the layer quality and the examination of the best process parameters for deposition, all specimens are investigated using microscopic methods. The characterisation of uncoated and single/multi-layer coated carbon fibres was carried out by means of microscopic and spectroscopic analyses.

3.1 Characterisation of the microstructure

Optical microscopy and SEM studies were used to identify layer structures including imperfections and to describe the interface of consecutive layers. Using EDX analysis, the occurrence of diffusion effects was investigated. The investigations also include TEM observations for better interface analyses. Special FIB-TEM preparation techniques were carried out for the preparation of 100 nm thick, electron-transparent thin films of single fibres and multi-layer microsensor fibres. These techniques have been developed at the Institute of Materials Science and Engineering. They incorporate the options of a high preparation speed and excellent thin-film quality [10].

Figure 3: SEM images of multi layer coated carbon fibres – **a** full cross section showing a HTA 5131 carbon fibre (core), the Cr layer (50 nm), the NiFe45/55 layer, the Si_3N_4 layer (dark) and the outer Cu layer; **b** magnified section of **a** showing intact layers; **c** lateral view of the same layer system (low degree of Cu crystallisation).

Figure 4: SEM images of outer Cu layers deposited by cathode sputtering on a multilayer carbon fibre – **a** crystalline Cu surface; **b** cross section of the Cu layer showing crystallite growth only in the outside area of the layer

Furthermore, the measurement of residual stresses in the different layers of the multilayer fibres was carried out by means of X-ray dif-fraction, using the $\sin(2\psi)$ method. This method exploits the correlation between the elastic strains in a certain direction and the shifts of the atomic-lattice spacing. Diffraction patterns of samples with perpendicular versus parallel orientation of the fibres to the surface were compared in order to determine the peak shifts [11]. These measurements additionally allow conclusions about the presence of different phases in the layer structure, particularly in the NiFe45/55 and Cu layer.

3.2 Mechanical characterisation

Mechanical tests of single fibres complete the characterisation of multi layer microsensors. These tests are carried out using the single fibre tension test, developed by the company Kammrath & Weiß. The tension tests include testing of carbon fibres in as received state, testing of pretreated carbon fibres to determine harming influences of preparation processes (desizing, heat treatment) and testing of layer structures deposited on carbon fibres. The influence of every single layer is tested comparing test results of fibres with and without this certain layer. The objective of the mechanical tension tests is the determination of influences on the mechanical properties induced by heat treatment or deposition processes.

Furthermore it is necessary to implement tension test underlying certain temperature profiles to investigate the temperature behaviour of different layers as well as the temperature behaviour of the multi-layer system. There is a significant influence of the temperature to the sensitivity of the magnetoelastic microsensor.

3.3 Results of the microstructural characterisation

NiFe45/55 layers show a homogeneous dispersion of the coating and an excellent coupling to the carbon fibre due to Cr layer acting as a coupling agent (Fig. 3 b, 5 c). A good coupling of NiFe45/55 to the carbon fibre is of high importance. The best microsensor sensitivity, the strongest change in the magnetic permeability and a correct strain measurement can only be reached if the NiFe45/55 layer elongates the same way the carbon fibre does. Some specimens show pores, oriented in radial direction. Shadow

Figure 5: STEM images of coated carbon fibres – **a** Si_3N_4 (bright, amorphous), Cr and Cu (orientation contrast, crystalline) layer, **b** overview of the coated carbon fibre, **c** magnified image of the Cr coupling layer

effects are responsible for an irregular layer growth on the fibre side not facing the sputter target. On fibre surfaces with a strongly grooved structure, this effect is intense (bottom of fig. 3 a). During the sputtering of NiFe45/55 from one side, voids formed in the first deposition step provoke the formation of even bigger voids in the following deposition steps after rotating the fibre. Therefore, the usage of carbon fibres with a smooth surface is recommended. Further on, the effect of coatings with pyrolytic carbon on the smoothening of the surface will be examined. An interface between the single NiFe45/55 layers was found. Oxidation processes occurring while the sample is emerged to air during manual rotation are probably responsible. Therefore, an automatic rotation within the closed and evacuated recipient is strongly recommended to achieve better layer qualities. Different cooling times are probably responsible for the degree of oxidation and therefore responsible for the occurrence of interphases. The microstructure of NiFe45/55 layers is uniformly crystalline. Crystallites are mainly oriented in radial direction or preferably in the direction of the sputter target. Grain boundaries and contact twins can easily be found and distinguished.

Si_3N_4 layers show a poor coupling to the NiFe45/55 layer. Cavities are found in the interface between both layers. In layers with thicknesses above $2 \mu\text{m}$, the appearance of radially oriented cracks can be observed. These cracks result from residual stress induced by different coefficients of thermal expansion of the layer material and the substrate. Due to cooling-down from the process temperature of the PECVD process, the layer tends to shrink. Since shrinkage is limited because of the given shape of the NiFe45/55 surface, residual stress is developed. If this stress exceeds the critical limit, cracks occur in the layer. This effect can be omitted by the reduction of the layer thickness or by lowering the process temperature. Poor coupling of the Si_3N_4 layer does not necessarily disturb the microsensors function. Through the additional Cr layer between Si_3N_4 and NiFe45/55 layer the coupling characteristic can be improved. If the inner microsensors core (carbon fibre and NiFe45/55 layer) only slides within the Si_3N_4 layer, the microsensors stiffness will be reduced. The micro-structure of Si_3N_4 layers is homogeneous and shows no pores or voids. Compared to NiFe45/55 and Cu layers, no distinct crystallite structure can be observed (see fig. 5 a, b).

The investigation of cathode-sputtered Cu layers shows varying properties when comparing different samples. Some samples feature a porous structure and some others consist of bulk crystallites sticking together like cauliflower florets (Fig. 5 b). Present

specimens in contrast show unique layer properties (Fig. 5 a). The outer layer surface is strongly crystalline (Fig. 4 a). The core features a homogeneous Cu distribution (Fig. 4 b). Generally Cu layers are strongly crystalline (Fig. 5 a). Single crystallites measure up to a few micrometers in diameter. The formation of growth twins and dislocations can be observed (Fig 5 a). The number of voids has immensely decreased compared to first samples. But the shadow effect, already observed for the NiFe45/55 layer, responsible for pore growth in radial direction can be found in Cu layers as well. It is strongly recommended to use an automated rotating holder for the PVD process in future deposition experiments. The oxidation of Cu layers will probably be even stronger than for NiFe45/55 and therefore defect development will be even worse. In order to eliminate oxidation processes, the holder equipment will be changed to allow fibre rotation under high-vacuum conditions.

3.4 Results of the mechanical characterisation

Thick layers (thicknesses above 1 μm) have a strong influence on the stiffness of the microsensor fibre. If the applied load exceeds the maximum tensile strength of the multilayer microsensor, fibre breakage occurs at random places. For layer thicknesses below 1 μm , the stiffness of the fibre dominates the overall mechanical properties. Force-path curves of single-fibre tensile tests measuring multilayer microsensor fibres are comparable to curves of uncoated fibres. Comparing stress-strain curves of coated and uncoated carbon fibres absorbability can be observed for coated fibres at low strain rates (see fig. 6 b). The reason of this effect can mainly be seen in plastic deformation of the layer. Interface characteristics may also lead to these characteristics. But since a perfect layer coupling was observed in SEM and TEM studies, plastic deformation is seen responsible. Out of these considerations it can be concluded that actual NiFe45/55 layers have an elastic limit below 1%. Fibre breakage with fibres carrying thin layers occurs mainly at the fixation, like for uncoated fibres. In dynamic single-fibre tensile tests of coated microsensor fibres, a hysteresis can be observed. This is an evidence of plastic deformation within metallic layers. Plastic deformation may lead to a shorter life cycle of the microsensor. Residual stress reduces the area of elastic deformation. Therefore, the characterisation of residual stress is of high importance. High strain rates result in breakage of the ceramic Si_3N_4 layer. Applying cyclic loads, a destruction of ceramic layers could occur, influencing the over-all microsensor function. Further investigations are necessary to give a separate proof. An intense and repeatable influence of fibre preparation processes (heating, desizing) could not be found. Comparing fibres of the as-received state and desized fibres, an insignificant change in mechanical properties can be found (comp. fig. 6 a). This confirms past investigations [12]. The thermal treatment for desizing seems to improve the tensile strength. This process leads to a deposition of carbon on the fibre surface, which improves the mechanical properties. The deposition of chromium by means of cathode sputtering does not negatively influence the mechanical characteristics of carbon fibres. The positive effects of pyrolytic carbon on the mechanical properties described in [11] will be proved and compared to the influences of the thermal treatment in subsequent experiments. The same applies for negative effects of ceramic layers on the fibre strength [12].

Figure 6: Results of single fibre tensile tests – **a** comparison of the tensile strength of different fibre types after different treatments (acetone treatment, thermal treatment, chromium deposition), **b** stress-strain curves of an uncoated T800 fibre and a T800 fibre coated with NiFe45/55

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Manufacture of the magnetoelastic microsensor using PVD and PECVD process is possible. By combining a fibre turning lathe and FIB machining, a new method for creating a Cu coil could be created and already proofed successfully. All layers show a satisfactory quality required for fabricating a magnetoelastic microsensor. The NiFe45/55 layer shows the highest quality, a remarkably crystalline structure, and except for some oxidation defectless interfaces. The Si_3N_4 layer with a thickness of approx. 1 μm features a homogeneous structure and shows no cracks. The quality of copper layers is high and promises to form an appropriate coil. The single-fibre strain strongly depends on the layer thickness. An improvement of the layer quality is necessary. Continuing the described investigations, the quality of deposition results will be raised and reasons for partially poor layer properties will be located. The manufacture of first microsensor prototypes enables experiments seeking for an optimal integration of microsensors into composite materials and for the best contacting methods. Subsequent investigations will deal with the microsensor calibration and its characterisation. The microsensor calibration will be carried out by means of the single-fibre tensile test.

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